

**SLEEP QUALITY AND PSYCHOLOGICAL WELL-BEING OF BOARDING
SECONDARY SCHOOL STUDENTS IN THE ARCHDIOCESE OF BAMENDA,
NORTH WEST REGION, CAMEROON**

By

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ABSTRACT

There are increasing numbers of secondary school students in Cameroon suffering from poor sleep quality and psychological problems. There have been many complaints from students and teachers about boarding secondary school students sleeping in class when lessons are going on. The study therefore explored the relationship between sleep quality and student's psychological well-being in Cameroon. The study aimed at achieving the following specific objectives: To examine the relationship between sleep quality and psychological well-being of students, in boarding secondary schools in the Archdiocese of Bamenda, North West Region, Cameroon. The study was guided by Oswald's Restoration Theory of Sleep (1931) and Maslow's Hierarchy of Needs (1943). The study used mixed method, specifically embedded research design. The instruments used were Sleep Quality Scale (SQS) by Yi et al (2006), the brief scale of psychological well-being for adolescents (PWBS) by Viejo et al (2018) and three open-ended questions for interview. A descriptive statistic was used for data analysis, with the results presented in tables and figures as frequencies and percentages, mean, standard deviations and summaries presented as Pearson's (r) correlational coefficient. The findings revealed that the participants enjoy quality sleep with high psychological well-being: In addition, there is a significant positive relationship between sleep quality and psychological well-being. Strategies to enhance student's psychological well-being were

suggested. It is recommended that principals continue to prioritize sleep hygiene practices, self-care and implement structured schedules that allow for adequate rest alongside academic demands.

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Introduction

Sleep is crucial for human well-being, with poor or disordered sleep leading to impairments in cognitive and psychological functioning. Millions of people suffer from inadequate sleep, causing serious health consequences. Sleep is essential for the body's proper functioning and promotes growth, learning, and cognitive functions. Restoring sleep is strongly correlated with better overall health. Sleep quality measures how well you sleep, while sleep satisfaction is subjective. Adults should sleep 7-9 hours, while school-aged children and teenagers should get 11 hours. Sleep deprivation increases the likelihood of poor grades, anxiety, depression, and suicidal thoughts. Poor sleep quality is associated with poor psychological well-being, and falling asleep within 30 minutes of getting into bed is a sign of high-quality sleep. Adequate sleep is crucial for students' emotional, behavioral, and cognitive abilities, as well as their academic development and physical activity levels. Sleep is essential for maintaining physiological health and cognitive functions. Sleep deprivation can lead to anxiety, depression, daytime fatigue, sleepiness, energy loss, emotional disturbance, poor grades, academic failure, compromised learning, impaired mood, and increased risk of accidents. It is essential for secondary school students to get adequate sleep to maintain their psychological well-being and avoid negative consequences. Sleep quality is a

crucial aspect of overall health, encompassing initiating, maintaining, restoring, waking up, and daytime symptoms. Good sleep is restful and restorative, with an ideal quality of 85% or more. Poor sleep quality, insomnia, and daytime sleepiness are prevalent among students, with an international average of 58% among 8th graders and 47% among 4th graders. Factors contributing to sleep deprivation include social, cultural, environmental, and biological factors. To improve student sleep quality, a collaborative effort from all stakeholders is needed, including paying attention to students' sleeping patterns. In Rwanda, poor sleep quality is particularly prevalent among medical students, with final and first-year students reporting the worst sleep quality. Lemogoum et al. (2021) found a significant association between short sleep duration and poor sleep quality with type 2 diabetes prevalence in Cameroon. However, there is a lack of research on sleep quality and psychological well-being among students in Africa, particularly in Cameroon. Poor sleep quality can lead to psychological problems, and school authorities are focusing on academic pursuits over other aspects of a student's life. This has led to concerns about student sleep quality in secondary schools in Cameroon, potentially impacting mental health and academic achievement.

Research Objectives

The study examined the relationship between sleep quality and psychological well-being of boarding secondary school students in the Archdiocese of Bamenda, North West Region, Cameroon.

Research Methodology

The study adopted the embedded research design. The embedded research design is a mixed method design, where one data provides a supportive, secondary role in a study primarily based on the data type. Mixed method research offers connections between the variables with the purpose of enhancing, ratifying, disconfirming or certifying results of a single study (Kanga et al.

2015). Descriptive research describes the status of an identified variable. The quantitative method of research provided a supportive, secondary role in a primarily based on quantitative method. The qualitative method is therefore embedded into quantitative method (Creswell et al. 2018). sleep quality was explored through phone calls interview with school counselor and principals, looking at psychological well-being. The research design enabled the researcher to have access to the participant' feelings and thoughts which led to a better comprehension of the meaning that the participants attributed to their experiences of sleep quality and psychological well-being. However, qualitative data was secondary to quantitative data. According to Creswell et al. (2018), mixed method combines inductive and deductive thinking, therefore enriching the study by providing more comprehensive evidence.

The target population is 2,560 participants from college A, college B and college C (Data from College Records according to the principals, 2023). The researcher used simple random sampling to select 3 functional boarding secondary schools out of the 7 boarding secondary schools in the Archdiocese of Bamenda, North West Region Cameroon. The study used proportionate sampling technique to select the students from the schools and 259 participated in the study.

The questionnaire had two standard tools adopted from Sleep Quality Scale (SQS) developed by Yi et al (2006) and the brief scale of psychological Well-Being for adolescents (BSPWB-A) developed by Viejo et al (2018).The (SQS) is a self-administered instrument made up of 28 items; The questionnaire for students were subdivided into three sections: Section A sought the demographic information; Section B tested students' sleep quality by using Sleep

Quality Scale (SQS) Section C measured Students' psychological well-being using Viejo four dimensions of psychological well-being.

The researcher was obligated to ensure that the respondents and the information they provided during the period of the study were protected and handled with care and accountability by storing the questionnaires safely for the duration of time they were needed before being destroyed. Similarly, the participants' identity remained anonymous and confidential. Similarly, information derived from participants were treated with utmost confidentiality and they were requested not to write their names on the questionnaire. The study ensured that the confidentiality of data, anonymity, privacy and safety of participants was observed and maintained by assuring the participants that the data they provided would remain confidential and would not be disclosed in any manner without their consent.

Anonymity implies that the researcher made sure that information derived from the participants could not be traced back to them. Hence, any personal identification information such as names, phone numbers, address, email, among others were not required. Considering the delicate nature of the target participants, namely, adolescent students, in case of any harmed or discomfort arising from the study a professional counselor was present to offer counseling services to the participant (s).

Findings

The demographic information about the respondent were presented followed by the questionnaire return rate from the respondents. The analysis of the data based on the relationship

between sleep quality and psychological well-being was done using Pearson correlation and presented in tables and figures.

Table 1

Demographic Information for quantitative data

<u>Variables</u>	<u>Frequency</u>	<u>Percentage (%)</u>
<u>Gender</u>		
Male	173	68.1
Female	81	31.9
Total	254	100
<u>Age</u>		
12-14yrs	43	16.9
15-18yrs	178	68.9
20 and above	36	14.2
Total	254	100
<u>Respective Schools</u>		
Collage A	133	44.5
Collage B	128	50.4
Collage C	13	5.1
Total	254	100

Results from Table 1 show that majority of the respondents are male students aged 15 – 18 years. The results also indicate that more than three quarter of the respondents came from the first two schools (A & B).

Table 2

Participants Demographic Information for Qualitative Data

Categories	Age	Gender	Qualification	Teaching Experience
Participant 1	21-25	Male	Degree	1-5years
Participant 2	26-30	Male	Degree	1-5years
Participant 3	31-40	Female	Masters	6-10years
Participant 4	41 and above	Female	Degree	11-15years
Participant 5	41 and above	Male	PHD	16 and above

According to the statistics from Table 2, gender distribution of the respondents was very necessary in the qualitative collection of data. This was to enable the researcher to collect reliable information and to ensure that the findings of the study were not gender biased. The principals and counsellors interviewed are highly qualified and experienced teachers and administrators.

The relationship between sleep quality and psychological well-being

This study employed Pearson Correlation to determine the relationship between sleep quality and psychological well-being of boarding secondary schools in the Archdiocese of Bamenda, North West Region, Cameroon.

Table 3

Correlation of Sleep Quality and Psychological Well-Being

PSYWB

SLEEPQ

PSYWB	Pearson Correlation	1	.271**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000
	N	254	254
SLEEPQ	Pearson Correlation	.271**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	
	N	254	254

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

The results from table 3 show the Pearson Correlation value of .271** indicating a positive correlation between Psychological Well-Being and Sleep Quality. There is a relationship between sleep quality and psychological well-being among the boarding secondary school students. This finding agrees with Su et al. (2023) which maintains that sleep quality can directly enhance the subjective well-being of boarding secondary school students in the Archdiocese of Bamenda Northwest Region, Cameroon and can also indirectly affect it through resilience.

According to Suet al (2023), the results suggest that sleep quality can directly enhance the subjective well-being of college students and can also indirectly affect it through resilience. Additionally, belief in a just world can enhance the promoting effect of resilience on the subjective well-being of college students. These findings may contribute to understanding the impact of sleep quality on the subjective well-being of college students and its pathways. These research findings can serve as a reference for improving the subjective well-being of college students.

Discussion

The study established that there is a significant positive relationship between sleep quality and psychological well-being among boarding secondary school students of the Archdiocese of Bamenda. Strategies such as creating conducive sleep environments, addressing external distractions, and promoting sleep education were highlighted as essential for improving student sleep quality.

Participant perspectives emphasized the multifaceted nature of sleep quality and the interconnectedness of physical, emotional, and cognitive well-being, underscoring the need for tailored interventions. The significance of quality rest was emphasized, addressing external factors like distractions from technology and social interactions. Encouraging healthy sleep habits, balanced schedules, and personalized support for students facing sleep challenges emerged as key recommendations to enhance overall well-being through improved sleep quality.

Discussions on improving sleep quality among students in boarding schools emphasized key strategies such as education on the importance of sleep, creating conducive sleep environments, balancing academic demands with rest, and providing personalized support for students facing sleep challenges. By promoting awareness, advocating for healthy sleep habits, and addressing individual needs, the participants highlighted the importance of a comprehensive approach to enhancing student well-being through better sleep quality in boarding secondary schools in the Archdiocese of Bamenda.

Recommendations

1. Principals of boarding schools are encouraged to shape the sleep environment for students.

2. It is recommended that principals prioritize sleep hygiene practices, self-care and implement structured schedules that allow for adequate rest alongside academic demands.
3. Creating dormitory conditions that are conducive to for sleep, such as ensuring a quiet and comfortable atmosphere, can significantly impact students' sleep quality.
4. Providing resources for stress management and promoting mental well-being initiatives can also contribute to better sleep outcomes among students.

Conclusion

The study concludes that there is a significant relationship between sleep quality and psychological well-being students. It is crucial to prioritize healthy sleep habits for general mental health due to the significant correlation found between psychological wellbeing and quality of sleep. Poor sleep quality is known to have a detrimental effect on psychological wellbeing and to exacerbate mood disorders, anxiety, and stress. Students can increase their psychological well-being and general quality of life by working on enhancing the quality of their sleep through good sleep hygiene habits and treating any underlying sleep problems. There is a need to be aware of the connection between sleep and mental health. Taking proactive measures to make sure that students obtain restorative sleep is necessary for the best possible psychological functioning.

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